

A regime shift in Southeast Greenland

Heide-Jørgensen, M.P.¹⁾, P. Chambault^{1,2)}, T. Jansen^{1,3)}, C.V.B. Gjelstrup³⁾, A. Rosing-Asvid⁴⁾, A. Macrander⁵⁾, G. Víkingsson †⁵⁾, X. Zhang⁶⁾, C. S. Andresen⁷⁾, B.R. MacKenzie³⁾,

1) Greenland Institute of Natural Resources, Strandgade 91, 2, DK-1401 Copenhagen K, Denmark

2) Department of Ecology and Evolutionary Biology, The University of California, Santa Cruz, CA, United States

3) DTU Aqua, Institute of Aquatic Resources, Kemitorvet, Bygning 201, DK-2800 Kongens Lyngby

4) Greenland Institute of Natural Resources, Kivioq 2, DK-3900 Nuuk, Greenland

5) Marine and Freshwater Research Institute, Fornubúðum 5, 220 Hafnarfjörður, 101 Reykjavík, Ísland

6) International Arctic Research Center, Department of Atmospheric Sciences, University of Alaska Fairbanks, Fairbanks, AK 99775, USA

7) GEUS, Øster Voldgade 10, DK-1350 København K

† Deceased

Supplementary Material

Fig. S1. Map of the coastal area of Southeast Greenland used for extracting remote sensing information on SST, SIC and MLD.

Fig. S2. Temporal variability in the summer averaged Storis Index (June-July-August) since 1820 and, together with regime-specific means identified by a sequential regime shift detection algorithm (Rodionov and Overland 2015; Rodionov 2016). The indices for the series starting in 1820 are standardized indices derived using averages for the period 1820-2021, respectively. Black line with dots: standardized Storis index for June-August; red line: regime-specific means. See Methods for details.

Trends in SST along Southeast Greenland

Fig. S3. Trends in SST values from 9 different areas (see Supplementary Material figure S1) along Southeast Greenland from 1990 through 2020. The dashed lines represent the southern region 5 to 9 and the full lines represent the northern region (1-4). The series are extracted from the ORAS5 product: <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-oras5?tab=overview> for the August.

Fig. S4. North Atlantic Oscillation representing the difference in atmospheric pressure between Iceland and Portugal. The index was obtained from NAO the Climate Analysis Section, NCAR, Boulder, USA, (Hurrell 2003).

Fig. S5. Loess plot of the time series of ocean reanalysis (ORAS5) temperature data from Faxafloi Station 9 (Fx9, 64.2N 28W, Fig.1) from 1990 through 2020. The series are extracted from the ORAS5 product: <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-oras5?tab=overview> averaged over the 0-200m depth interval for the July-September period. A linear regression

a)

b)

Fig. S6. A: Historical distribution of capelin around Iceland, and B: recent distribution. Red arrows represent spawning migrations to spawning areas. Light blue arrows represent drift of 0-group in nursery areas. Green arrows show migrations of maturing fish in to feeding areas. Dark blue arrows represent migration to overwintering areas. (from Jansen et al. 2021a).

Figure S6. Positions of six humpback whales in September 2019 and 2021 on the East Greenland shelf, with bathymetry (upper panel) and map with sea surface temperature for the two whales in 2021 (lower panel).

Table S1. Age at maturity for some fish species and marine mammals occurring in the East Greenland shelf and shelf-break region.

Species	Age at maturity (yr)	Reference	Species	Age at sexual maturity (yr)	Reference
Bluefin tuna, <i>Thunnus thynnus</i>	4-5	ICCAT 2020	Narwhal, <i>Monodon monoceros</i>	9	Garde et al. 2021
Atlantic mackerel, <i>Scomber scombrus</i>	2-3	ICES 2021	Fin whale, <i>Balaenoptera physalus</i>	10	Lockyer and Sigurjónsson 1992
Capelin, <i>Mallotus villosus</i>	2-4	ICES 2021	Humpback whale, <i>Megaptera novaeangliae</i>	6	Clapham 2018
Polar cod, <i>Boreogadus saida</i>	1-2	Aune et al. 2021	Walrus, <i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	6	https://nammco.no/atlantic-walrus/#1475762140594-0925dd6e-f6cc
			Long-finned pilot whale, <i>Globicephala melas</i>	8	Bloch et al. 1993
			Minke whale, <i>Balaenoptera acutorostrata</i>	6	Haug et al. 2011
			White-beaked dolphin, <i>Lagenorhynchus albirostris</i>	8	Galatius and Kinze 2016
			Killer whale, <i>Orcinus orca</i>	13	https://nammco.no/killer-whale/#1475762140594-0925dd6e-f6cc
			Harp seal, <i>Pagophilus groenlandicus</i>	5	https://nammco.no/harp-seal/#1475762140594-0925dd6e-f6cc
			Hooded seal, <i>Cystophora cristata</i>	5	Frie et al. 2012

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